

Fractional-order Bernoulli wavelets for solving the fractional Bagley-Torvik equation arising in fluid mechanics

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Abstract

In this paper, a new numerical method for solving the fractional Bagley-Torvik equation is presented. The method is based upon fractional-order Bernoulli wavelets approximation. The Riemann-Liouville fractional integral operator for FBWs is introduced. This operator is then utilized to reduce the solution of the initial and boundary value problems for the fractional Bagley-Torvik differential equation to a system of algebraic equations.

Keywords: Fractional-order Bernoulli wavelets, Fractional Bagley-Torvik equation, Caputo derivative, Collocation method.

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1 Introduction

Fractional differential equations (FDEs) are generalizations of ordinary differential equations to an arbitrary (noninteger) order. FDEs have attracted considerable interest because of their ability to model complex phenomena such as continuum and statistical mechanics, visco-elastic materials, and solid mechanics. The Bagley-Torvik equation is first proposed by the authors of [6] and has an outstanding role of being a model of motion of a rigid plate immersed in a Newtonian fluid.

2 Preliminaries and notation

2.1 The fractional derivative and integral

Definition 2.1. The Riemann-Liouville fractional integral operator of order $\nu \geq 0$ is defined as [5]

$$I^\nu f(t) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\Gamma(\nu)} \int_0^t \frac{f(s)}{(t-s)^{1-\nu}} ds, & \nu > 0, t > 0, \\ f(t), & \nu = 0. \end{cases}$$

Definition 2.2. Caputo's fractional derivative of order ν is defined as [5]

$$D^\nu f(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(n-\nu)} \int_0^t \frac{f^{(n)}(s)}{(t-s)^{\nu+1-n}} ds, \quad n-1 < \nu \leq n, n \in \mathbb{N}.$$

For the Caputo derivative we have [5]

$$D^\nu I^\nu f(t) = f(t), \quad I^\nu D^\nu f(t) = f(t) - \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} f^{(i)}(0) \frac{t^i}{i!}.$$

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2.2 Fractional-order Bernoulli wavelets

The fractional-order Bernoulli wavelets (FBWs) $\psi_{n,m}^\alpha(x)$, $n = 1, 2, \dots, 2^{k-1}$, $m = 0, 1, 2, \dots, M - 1$ can be defined by introducing the change of variable $t = x^\alpha$ on the Bernoulli wavelets as [5]

$$\psi_{n,m}^\alpha(x) = \begin{cases} 2^{\frac{k-1}{2}} \tilde{\beta}_m(2^{k-1}x^\alpha - \hat{n}), & \frac{\hat{n}}{2^{k-1}} \leq x^\alpha < \frac{\hat{n}+1}{2^{k-1}}, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad 0 \leq x < 1, \quad (2.1)$$

with

$$\tilde{\beta}_m(2^{k-1}x^\alpha - \hat{n}) = \begin{cases} 1, & m = 0, \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{\frac{(-1)^{m-1}(m!)^2}{(2m)!}} \beta_{2m}} \beta_m(2^{k-1}x^\alpha - \hat{n}), & m > 0, \end{cases} \quad (2.2)$$

where $\hat{n} = n - 1$, k is assumed and positive integer and $\beta_m(t)$ are the well-known Bernoulli polynomials of order m which can be defined by [5].

2.3 Fractional-order Bernoulli functions

We define the fractional-order Bernoulli functions (FBFs) by transformation $t = x^\alpha$ based on the Bernoulli polynomials as [5]

$$\beta_m^\alpha(x) = \sum_{i=0}^m \binom{m}{i} \beta_{m-i} x^{i\alpha}, \quad 0 \leq x \leq 1, \quad (2.3)$$

where $\beta_i := \beta_i(0)$, $i = 0, 1, \dots, m$, are Bernoulli numbers. These functions satisfy the following formula [5]

$$\int_0^1 \beta_n^\alpha(x) \beta_m^\alpha(x) x^{\alpha-1} dx = \frac{1}{\alpha} (-1)^{n-1} \frac{m!n!}{(m+n)!} \beta_{m+n}, \quad m, n \geq 1. \quad (2.4)$$

3 Function approximations and operational matrices

We can expand any function $f \in L^2[0, 1)$ into truncated fractional-order Bernoulli wavelets series as

$$f(x) \simeq \sum_{n=1}^{2^{k-1}} \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} c_{nm} \psi_{nm}^\alpha(x) = C^T \Psi^\alpha(x), \quad (3.1)$$

where C and $\Psi^\alpha(x)$ are $\hat{m} \times 1$, ($\hat{m} = 2^{k-1}M$) matrices, given by

$$C = [c_{1,0}, c_{1,1}, \dots, c_{1,M-1}, \dots, c_{2^{k-1},0}, \dots, c_{2^{k-1},M-1}]^T,$$

$$\Psi^\alpha(x) = [\psi_{1,0}^\alpha(x), \psi_{1,1}^\alpha(x), \dots, \psi_{1,M-1}^\alpha(x), \dots, \psi_{2^{k-1},0}^\alpha(x), \dots, \psi_{2^{k-1},M-1}^\alpha(x)]^T.$$

The fractional-order Bernoulli wavelets can be expanded into M -set of fractional-order Bernoulli functions as

$$\Psi_{\hat{m} \times 1}^\alpha(x) = \Phi_{\hat{m} \times M} B_{M \times 1}^\alpha(x), \quad (3.2)$$

where Φ is the transformation matrix of FBWs to FBFs and the fractional-order Bernoulli functions vector $B^\alpha(x)$ is defined as $B^\alpha(x) = [\beta_0^\alpha(x), \beta_1^\alpha(x), \dots, \beta_{M-1}^\alpha(x)]^T$.

Fractional integration of the fractional-order Bernoulli functions vector is given as

$$I^\nu B^\alpha(x) = F^{(\nu,\alpha)} B^\alpha(x), \quad (3.3)$$

where $F_{M \times M}^{(\nu, \alpha)}$ is the fractional-order Bernoulli functions operational matrix of the fractional order integration [5]. Recently, Rahimkhani and et al. [5] have derived the fractional-order Bernoulli wavelets operational matrix of fractional order integration as following

$$(I^\nu \Psi^\alpha)(x) = P^{(\nu, \alpha)} \Psi^\alpha(x), \quad (3.4)$$

where $P_{\hat{m} \times \hat{m}}^{(\nu, \alpha)}$ is the fractional-order Bernoulli wavelets operational matrix of fractional order integration and can be obtained by substituting (3.2), (3.3) into (3.4) as

$$P_{\hat{m} \times \hat{m}}^{(\nu, \alpha)} = \Phi_{\hat{m} \times M} F_{M \times M}^{(\nu, \alpha)} \Phi_{M \times \hat{m}}^{-1}. \quad (3.5)$$

4 Problem statement

In this paper, we focus on the following Bagley-Torvik problems

Problem 1.

$$\begin{cases} AD^2y(x) + BD^{\frac{3}{2}}y(x) + Wy(x) = f(x), & 0 \leq x \leq 1, \\ y(0) = y_0, & y'(0) = y'_0. \end{cases} \quad (4.1)$$

Problem 2.

$$\begin{cases} AD^2y(x) + BD^{\frac{3}{2}}y(x) + Wy(x) = f(x), & 0 \leq x \leq 1, \\ y(0) = y_0, & y(1) = y_1. \end{cases} \quad (4.2)$$

5 Numerical method

In this section, we use the fractional-order Bernoulli wavelets for solving problems 1 and 2. First, we expand $D^2y(x)$ by FBWs as

$$D^2y(x) \simeq C^T \Psi^\alpha(x). \quad (5.1)$$

By using Eqs. (3.5) and (5.1), we have

$$y(x) \simeq C^T P^{(2, \alpha)} \Psi^\alpha(x) + y_0 + y'_0 x, \quad D^{\frac{3}{2}}y(x) \simeq C^T P^{(\frac{1}{2}, \alpha)} \Psi^\alpha(x). \quad (5.2)$$

Substituting Eqs. (5.1) and (5.2) in problems 1 and 2, we get

$$AC^T \Psi^\alpha(x) + B(C^T P^{(\frac{1}{2}, \alpha)} \Psi^\alpha(x)) + W(C^T P^{(2, \alpha)} \Psi^\alpha(x) + y_0 + y'_0 x) = f(x). \quad (5.3)$$

For problem 2, we get: $y'_0 = y_1 - (C^T P^{(2, \alpha)} \Psi^\alpha(1) + y_0)$.

Next, we collocate Eq. (5.3) at $x_i = \frac{2i-1}{2\hat{m}}, i = 1, 2, \dots, \hat{m}$. The resulting equations give $\hat{m}$ algebraic equations, which can be solved for the unknown vector C^T .

6 Numerical examples

Example 6.1. Consider the Bagley-Torvik equation with boundary conditions [7]

$$\begin{cases} D^2y(x) + D^{\frac{3}{2}}y(x) + y(x) = 1 + x, & 0 \leq x \leq 1, \\ y(0) = 1, & y(1) = 2. \end{cases} \quad (6.1)$$

The exact solution is given by $y(x) = 1 + x$.

$$D^2y(x) \simeq c_{10}\psi_{10}^\alpha(x) + c_{20}\psi_{2,0}^\alpha(x) = \tilde{C}^T\tilde{\Psi}^\alpha(x). \quad (6.2)$$

$$y(x) \simeq \tilde{C}^T P^{(2,\alpha)}\tilde{\Psi}^\alpha(x) + 1 + (1 - (\tilde{C}^T P^{(2,\alpha)}\tilde{\Psi}^\alpha(1)))x, \quad D^{\frac{3}{2}}y(x) \simeq \tilde{C}^T P^{(\frac{1}{2},\alpha)}\tilde{\Psi}^\alpha(x). \quad (6.3)$$

Substituting Eqs. (6.2) and (6.3) into Eq. (6.1). Next we collocate this equation at points $\frac{1}{4}, \frac{3}{4}$. Then we obtain $c_{10} = c_{20} = 0$. Hence, for $k = 2, M = 1$ and $\alpha = \frac{1}{2}$, the approximate solution of Example 6.1, is given $y(x) = 1 + x$, which is the exact solution of this equation.

Example 6.2. Consider the Bagley-Torvik equation with boundary conditions ([2], [1])

$$\begin{cases} D^{\frac{3}{2}}y(x) + y(x) = \frac{2\sqrt{x}}{\Gamma(\frac{3}{2})} + x(x-1), & 0 \leq x \leq 1, \\ y(0) = y(1) = 0. \end{cases} \quad (6.4)$$

The exact solution is given by $y(x) = x^2 - x$. In Table 1, we compare the absolute error obtained using the proposed method for $k = 1, M = 5$, and $\alpha = \frac{1}{2}$ with the Pseudo-spectral method [2] and Bashforth-Moulton method [1].

Table 1: Comparison of absolute errors for Example 6.2.

x	<i>Our method</i>	<i>Pseudospectral method</i>	<i>Bashforth – Moulton method</i>
0	7.69×10^{-14}	–	–
0.2	5.63×10^{-15}	–	–
0.4	7.69×10^{-14}	–	–
0.6	1.54×10^{-13}	–	–
0.8	1.48×10^{-13}	–	–
1	2.22×10^{-16}	6.83×10^{-4}	3.42×10^{-3}

Example 6.3. Consider the Bagley-Torvik equation with initial conditions [4]

$$\begin{cases} D^2y(x) + D^{\frac{3}{2}}y(x) + y(x) = \frac{15}{4}\sqrt{x} + \frac{15}{8}\sqrt{\pi}x + x^2\sqrt{x}, & 0 \leq x \leq 1, \\ y(0) = y'(0) = 0. \end{cases} \quad (6.5)$$

The exact solution is given by $y(x) = x^2\sqrt{x}$. Numerical results for $k = 2, M = 6$ and different values of α are given in Table 2.

Table 2: Comparison of numerical results for different values α for Example 6.3.

x	$\alpha = \frac{1}{2}$	$\alpha = 1$	$\alpha = \frac{3}{2}$	$\alpha = 2$
0	1.88×10^{-10}	2.99×10^{-5}	8.73×10^{-4}	2.54×10^{-2}
0.2	9.48×10^{-11}	3.22×10^{-4}	7.42×10^{-4}	1.44×10^{-2}
0.4	2.73×10^{-9}	5.84×10^{-4}	1.66×10^{-3}	3.31×10^{-4}
0.6	3.74×10^{-9}	1.09×10^{-2}	1.25×10^{-2}	2.08×10^{-1}
0.8	4.77×10^{-9}	1.36×10^{-2}	3.96×10^{-2}	6.43×10^{-2}

Example 6.4. Consider the Bagley-Torvik equation with initial conditions [3]

$$\begin{cases} D^2y(x) + D^{\frac{3}{2}}y(x) + y(x) = 8, & 0 \leq x \leq 1, \\ y(0) = y'(0) = 0. \end{cases} \quad (6.6)$$

In Table 3, by choosing $k = 1$, $M = 9$ and $\alpha = \frac{1}{2}$, we compare our results with the Adomian method and Taylor matrix method .

Table 3: Comparison of numerical results for Example 6.4.

x	<i>Exact solution</i>	<i>Adomian method</i>	<i>Taylor method</i>	<i>Our method</i>
0	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
0.2	0.125221	0.140640	0.125254	0.125221
0.4	0.455435	0.533284	0.455468	0.455435
0.6	0.950392	1.148840	0.950398	0.950393
0.8	1.579557	1.963033	1.579689	1.579557
1	2.315526	2.952567	2.315589	2.315525

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